

Data Problems in the Humanities, or "When everybody is special, no one is"?

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That the humanities has ‘a data problem’ is now a common refrain amongst many communities. Humanists often argue that humanities data is a problem because they don’t have or work with data (Borgman, 2010; Posner, 2015). Librarians and information professionals, by contrast, believe that humanists have data, but assume they don’t realize it — meaning that the problem is that they must be trained to appropriately recognize and work with data they most surely have (Flanders, Julia, and Trevor Muñoz, 2012; Ikeshoji-Orlati, Caton, and Stringer-Hye, 2018). Digital humanists know that they (at least) have data, but believe that their data are special, distinct both from those used by scientists and (often) those “not recognized” by traditional humanists — and that these data require special strategies and techniques as a result (Drucker, 2011; Schöch, 2013). In a rough and general way each premise informs a mélange of assumptions, advice and best practices that comprise the emerging literature on research data management (RDM) in the humanities.

In this paper we argue that this focus on the discovery and definition of what is “special” about the definition or recognition of humanities data is a mistake. Humanities data are not special because of what they are, but rather because of how they are used (Borgman, 2017; Leonelli, 2015). Data are data, in other words, whether they are produced and used by scientists or humanists. The “problem” with Humanities data — and the thing that makes them special — lies in the use-case. Humanities data are both designed and structured by systems to meet scholarly or systematic ends. While many humanities researchers engage, as users, with designed research infrastructure, humanities scholars also innovate, design, and build scholar-led research infrastructure that have specific systems requirements, but often without clear requirements modeling. We draw out the implications of this argument on two fronts, looking at the issue of research, and the implications for humanities infrastructure development.

First, we report on the preliminary results of ongoing research examining how humanists think about data as they build, navigate, and utilize research infrastructure for scholarly purposes. Reported results derive from a series of comparative case studies (Eisenhardt, 1989; Maryl et al. 2020) examining four cases of scholar-led projects that deploy digital research infrastructure for scholarly

ends. Cases were purposively selected using the following criteria: a. Are scholar-driven; b. Involve representation of ‘real world’ objects involving small, intensively curated datasets; c. Have a documented record of accomplishment and innovation.

Although humanists have a long history of designing and building research infrastructure, both analog and digital (Abbott, 2012; Bod, 2013) this has been less appreciated in the literature on humanities infrastructure design. By comparing elements from our case studies, we build on previous studies of humanists as both users of information resources (Bates, 1996a; 1996b; Bates et al., 1993; Buchanan, Gow, Blandford, Rimmer, and Warwick, 2006; Palmer, Teffeau, Pirmann, 2009; Stone, 1982; Rimmer, Warwick, Blandford, Gow, and Buchanan, G., 2008; Watson-Boone, 1994), and digital tools (Gibbs and Owens, 2022) to consider issues of use-case construction, both formally and informally, over time. Emphasizing the role of scholars as designers (Lamb and King, 2003; Millerand and Baker, 2010), we highlight the importance of the ‘use-case’ as a means to culturally frame and model system requirements, functional and non-functional, as a type of socio-technical fact, mediating between user-agency, the purpose of a scholarly project, and the design, development and maintenance of the research infrastructures innovated to meet those goals. Originating in software engineering, use-case modeling (Jacobson et al. 1992) is a means of specifying, validating, and eliciting system requirements, where use case models describe, communicate, and facilitate all of the ways a user interacting with a system or product may work to realize a desired end. While there is a robust literature on how to write and design use cases (Kulak, Daryl, and Guiney, 2012) there is little empirical study of use-case development or implementation in software engineering (Anda, 2003), and nothing that systematically examines the diffusion of the concept outside these arenas of expert work.

By comparing the roles of humanist researchers as designers, we complicate previous research on humanities work practices (Blanke and Hedges, 2013; Pachecho, 2022; Unsworth, 2000) and studies of interdisciplinary scholarly information practice more broadly (Palmer, 2013), drawing on the notion of ‘infrastructural practices’ (Baker and Millerand, 2016; Baker, Duerr, and Parsons, 2015; Edwards, 2019; Karasti and Blomberg, 2018) in scholarly information ecosystems (Altman and Cohen, 2022), and hence on the dual role of scholars as infrastructure designers-builders and users (Lamb and Kling, 2003; Millerand and Baer, 2010; Mongili, 2014).

While we acknowledge a few exceptions for specific tools and technical standards for the Digital Humanities (e.g. Voyant, TEI, IIIF, CIDOC CRM), the Humanities generally lack the proliferation of a robust, distributed, yet centrally networked, ecosystem supporting generalizable infrastructure development process, linking standards with the infrastructure practices central to scholar originated infrastructure projects (c.f. Bosman and Kramer, 2015). Rather, humanities researchers have worked far more improvisationally (Ciula, 2022), and in the absence of a systematic orientation to project requirements, have instead created custom knowledge infrastructure. As a result, the identification of discipline-wide standards for tools and infrastructure is far more difficult.

From the perspective of infrastructure design, development, and maintenance, therefore, the “problem of Humanities data” is how to support and interface with scholarly use-cases, the scenarios and problem sets scholars are concerned with, and engage with the custom infrastructural strategies they have developed to speak to them. In our conclusion, we point to some ways where a focus on use case modeling and system requirements planning can complement efforts to refine project development, particularly with refe-

rence to recent work on ‘data communities’ (Cooper and Springer, 2023) and community-oriented frameworks (Lyon, et. al 2012; Jeng and Oh, 2016; Jeng and He, 2022) to bring researchers and infrastructural partners into structured dialogue regarding requirements development.

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